

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE ADDUCTS OF DIBENZOYL SULPHIDE AND HALIDES OF ZINC, CADMIUM AND MERCURY

Adduct	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Analysis				Molecular Weight		Molar conductance ²⁵ ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹
			% Found		% Calc.		Found	Calc.	
			Halogen	Sulphur	Halogen	Sulphur			
Bz ₂ S ₂ .ZnCl ₂	Pale yellow	144	17.56	16.02	17.28	15.62	406.8	410.3	1.8
Bz ₂ S ₂ .ZnBr ₂	Yellow	128	31.98	12.14	32.00	12.84	482.4	499.2	1.5
Bz ₂ S ₂ .CdCl ₂	Straw yellow	136	15.88	14.38	15.49	14.02	432.8	457.3	3.3
Bz ₂ S ₂ .CdBr ₂	Deep yellow	114	28.88	12.36	29.25	11.73	522.3	546.2	3.1
(Bz ₂ S ₂) ₂ .HgCl ₂	Brownish yellow	172	7.96	15.46	8.65	15.64	782.8	819.6	1.0
(Bz ₂ S ₂) ₂ .HgBr ₂	Brown	158	18.21	14.60	17.59	14.12	892.6	908.4	1.7

ν (Hg-Cl) and at 270 cm⁻¹ for ν (Hg-Br) stretching modes are observed which are in agreement with the reported values in literature¹⁵ and are assigned to terminal metal-halogen stretching mode. The stoichiometric composition of the compound suggests an octahedral structure for these adducts. Many compounds of mercury (II) are known to have an octahedral structure^{11,16}. The possibility of polymeric structures through halogen or the ligand bridges is ruled out as polymeric structures with halogen or ligand bridging are expected to give bands at lower frequencies than those observed.

Thermogravimetric analysis of all these adducts show that all these compounds dissociate into their components at their melting points and at around 150° benzoyl halide and polysulphides of the metals are formed.

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Studies of 2,4-Dihydroxyvalerophenone Oxime as an Analytical Reagent : Part II—Gravimetric Determination of Copper and Nickel

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IN our earlier communication¹, conductometric, potentiometric, micro-analysis, i.r. and n.m.r. studies of the metal complexes of 2,4-dihydroxyvalerophenone oxime (DHVOX) were reported. The reagent has now been successfully employed for the gravimetric determination of copper and nickel and their separation from a large number of other ions. It has been found that the precipitation of copper and nickel as its complex starts at pH 2.5 and 6.0 and is quantitative in the pH range 3.0 to 10.0 and 6.5 to 9.5 respectively. The precipitated complex has been found to possess the composition M(C₁₁H₁₄NO₃)₂.

Experimental

All chemicals were of B.C.H., A.R. grade and were used without further purification. All pH measurements were made with Systronics pH meter (Model 322). Different pH were adjusted using acetic acid and ammonia buffer.

Results and Discussion

Determination of copper and nickel :

A number of reagents have been used for gravimetric determination of copper. The most important inorganic precipitant, viz., thiocyanate², suffers from the disadvantage of a low conversion factor and takes a long time (~ 6 hrs.) for complete precipitation.

In case of salicylaldoxime³ the metal precipitate can not be heated over 80° due to the decomposition of the reagent. Furthermore salicylaldoxime and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime⁴ complexes are partially soluble in ethanol. As a result, the excess of the reagent which gets precipitated is difficult to remove completely.

DHVOX has some advantages over these reagents. It is quite stable and can be kept at room temperature for months together without showing any sign of deterioration. After precipitation from the hot solutions, the metal precipitate can be digested on water bath for coagulation. The complexes of copper and nickel are insoluble in 60% ethanol and the excess of the reagent adhering to the complex can easily be washed out. The pH ranges for complete precipitation and also separation of copper and nickel are wider as compared to salicylaldoxime and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime.

An aqueous solution containing about 10 mg. of copper/nickel was diluted, heated to 80°–90° and was treated with 0.5% ethanolic solution of DHVOX (about twice the theoretical amount). The precipitate was filtered through a sintered glass crucible (G-4) after digestion on water bath for about half an hour. It was washed with hot water several times and finally with 20% ethanol and dried at 110°–120° to a constant weight. It has been found that the precipitation of copper/nickel as its complex starts at pH 2.5 and 6.0 and is quantitative in the pH range 3.0 to 10.0 and 6.5 to 9.5 respectively. The conversion factors (metal/metal complex) are 0.13250 and 0.12364 for copper and nickel respectively.

Determination of copper and nickel in presence of other ions :

Interference due to Sb³⁺, Bi³⁺, Fe³⁺ and As³⁺ was removed by adding tartaric acid (2 g.). By suitable adjustment of pH, about 5 to 10 times excess of a large number of cations e.g., Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺, Bi³⁺, Sb³⁺, As³⁺ at pH 3.0 and Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Mo⁶⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, W⁶⁺, U⁶⁺ at pH 4.0 could be tolerated in estimation of copper.

In the estimation of nickel, the interference has been removed by changing the pH of the reaction mixture, e.g., several cations like Zn²⁺, Mn²⁺ at pH 6.5; Cd²⁺, U⁶⁺, Mg²⁺, Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, Hg²⁺ at pH 7.0 and Fe³⁺, Sb³⁺, Bi³⁺, As³⁺ at pH 8.0 (from 4 to 10 times excess). About 10 to 100 times the molar excess of several anions, e.g., PO₄³⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, F⁻, B₄O₇²⁻, SO₄²⁻ and tartarate could be tolerated at pH 3.0 and 7.0 for copper and nickel estimations respectively.

Copper and nickel have also been accurately determined in different alloys (Brass, Aluminium-bronze, Manganese-bronze, high tensile brass, copper-nickel coin) at the above pH values and the percentage of copper and nickel obtained in different alloys agree with the reported values within experimental error.

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Synthesis of New Organometallic Compounds as Potential Pesticides. Part II

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THE organotin and organomercury compounds containing aliphatic chains have exhibited¹⁻³ potent antifungal and antibacterial activity. In continuation⁴ of our work on potential pesticides we have synthesised some cresyl alkyl ether which are reported in this communication.

Experimental

A series of forty two compounds were prepared through the following synthetic route⁴.

The substituted cresylalkyl ethers of tin and mercury were analysed for their Hg and Sn⁵ contents. Some of the compounds were also analysed for carbon and hydrogen and the values are given in Table 1.

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